

Introduction:

Hello, and thank you for agreeing to participate in this study. My name is [interviewer name], and I am a master's student at Paderborn University. We are conducting a research study titled "Security & privacy perceptions of Pakistani Facebook matrimony group users" with the primary objective of understanding the security and privacy challenges faced by users within these Facebook matrimonial groups.

Before we begin, I'd like to inform you that your participation is entirely voluntary, and you can withdraw at any time without any consequences. The interview will take approximately 40 to 50 minutes. With your permission, I would like to record our conversation to ensure accuracy in capturing your responses. All information you provide will be kept confidential and used solely for academic research purposes. Do you consent to participate in this interview and to have it recorded?